

Efficiency Improvements of Machining Processes based on Novel Simulation Developments and Detailed Process Chain Analyses

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Abstract

An increasing prioritization of efficient processes in machining production can be observed in order to focus on the aspect of sustainability in addition to economic machining. In the work presented here, optimization potential in the design and manufacture of tools and tool holders was identified based on novel simulation developments and detailed process and process chain analyses. For the efficient use of cooling lubricants in ejector deep hole drilling, the tool design could be adapted with the help of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) simulations. Another aspect is the development of advanced particle-damped tool holders, the use of which can significantly increase process stability during turning and milling. In a detailed process chain analysis, the manufacturing route of cemented carbide tools was investigated to identify energy consuming process steps and form a basis to optimize the resource-efficient reprocessing of the tools.

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1 Introduction

Manufacturing accounts for about 23% of global energy consumption [1] and thus has a major influence on the emission of climate-damaging CO₂ emissions. Rising energy and raw material prices and a growing awareness of environmental consequences place high demands on manufacturing processes. When developing more efficient machining processes, the focus is therefore increasingly on energy consumption throughout the entire process chain in addition to increasing productivity. This is reflected in a large number of publications in the field of machining, in which a wide range of experimental and simulative approaches are used to realize energy-efficient machining processes [2].

Machining processes are a complex interaction of tool holder, tool, workpiece and cooling lubricant and must be examined in detail in order to identify optimization potential. In addition to experimental analyses, modern simulation systems are capable of realistically mapping complex interrelationships and offer detailed insights. The potentials that can be identified with a new simulation and detailed process and process chain analyses in this paper range from the improvement of tool design with regard to cooling lubricant supply and the optimization of dynamic tool behavior through the modification of tool holders to the analysis of energy-intensive process steps in tool grinding. By taking into account the manufacture and reconditioning of the tools, the entire life cycle of a tool is considered in addition to its performance in use when evaluating and optimizing the energy efficiency of machining processes.

2 High productivity machining processes and resource-efficient use of cutting tools

When optimizing highly productive machining processes with regard to energy efficiency and the resource-saving use of tools, the energy consumption of the process itself must be considered on the one hand, while on the other hand there is potential in increasing the performance of the tools. With an average of 25.6 % of the total electrical energy used in machine tools, the cooling lubricant supply accounts for the largest share [3]. Modern and sophisticated methods of flow simulation allow complex processes such as ejector deep hole drilling to be analyzed with regard to optimizing the flow conditions. With the help of additive manufacturing, optimized tool geometries can be achieved that could not be produced conventionally.

When machining demanding materials, performance is often limited by the dynamic excitation of the tool, which has a negative impact in the form of chatter marks on the workpiece surface and increased tool wear. Here too, additive manufacturing provides the opportunity to increase the performance therefore the efficiency of cutting tools by allowing the integration of internal structures into tool holders that improve the dynamic tool behavior as particle dampers.

2.1 Efficient use of cooling lubricants based on Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics Simulations on the example of ejector deep hole drilling processes

Deep hole drilling processes place high demands on the cooling lubricant supply and typically require high pressures and large volume flows and therefore a correspondingly high pump capacity. In addition to cooling and lubricating the highly stressed cutting edges, the coolant must also ensure the safe removal of chips from the bore hole [4]. The cooling lubricant supply in these processes accounts for a large proportion of the electrical energy required. Reducing the required pressures and volume flows by gaining a precise understanding of the flow behavior and optimizing the tool geometry therefore has a high potential for significant energy savings and the realization of efficient drilling processes. Ejector deep hole drilling is a special deep hole drilling method. The process does not require any special machine equipment and can be carried out directly on machining centers or lathes [5]. The tool consists of a drill head and a double tube system (see left side of Fig. 1). The cooling lubricant is fed to the drill head in the annular channel between the inner tube and the boringbar and is discharged together with the chips through the chip mouths into the inner tube. The process does not require a sealing between the tool and the workpiece, as a negative pressure is generated in the inner tube due to the Venturi-principle by special ejector nozzles (Section B in Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Functional principle of ejector deep hole drilling (left), SPH flow simulation and additively manufactured drill head (right)

The grid-free approach of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) simulations is particularly suitable for the detailed analysis of the flow conditions during ejector deep hole drilling [6]. SPH is a meshless Lagrangian method in which the continuum medium is discretized by a collection of points, referred to as particles. In order to compute the physical attributes of fluid flow problems, SPH employs the solution of the Navier-Stokes (N-S) equations using the aforementioned points. This makes it possible to convert complex partial differential equations in time and space, such as the Lagrange form of the Navier-Stokes equations, into ordinary differential

equations that can be solved with standard integration algorithms and enables a physically correct and reliable simulation of the cooling lubricant flow in systems with free surfaces and changing topologies. The mesh-free nature of SPH enables the modeling of changing surfaces and interfaces with relative ease. This quality renders SPH an advantageous method for problems such as the modeling of ejector deep hole drilling, where the fluid domain is in a state of constant evolution, which is a significant computational challenge when attempting to track it using conventional mesh-based methods. The simulation of the fluid flow for ejector deep hole drilling commences with an initially empty geometry of borehole and drill head. A constant cooling liquid inflow is positioned at the outlet bores between the boring bar and the drill head with a laminar flow and a flow velocity of 5 m/s. This value is based on experimental data obtained through high-speed recordings using particle image velocity measurements (PIV). The inflow continuously introduces fluid particles into the simulation, while the outflow, situated within the inner tube, removes these particles from the simulation domain. Consequently, the requisite computational effort is diminished in comparison to a constant particle setup. Around 275,000 particles are used in the simulation domain for one simulation run. This is maintained until a nearly steady state of the flow is reached. The simulations require approximately 10 days on AMD5950X machines with 14 cores. The measurement of the flow in experimental investigations provides input data for the simulation on the one hand, but also serves to validate the simulation results on the other. Visual access to the coolant flow for the optical evaluation of the flow field with a high-speed camera system is made possible by a transparent ejector drilling system made of polycarbonate and the use of polyamide tracer particles in the coolant.

Taking into account the mechanical tool load caused by the feed force and drilling torque, drill heads with different modifications were designed. Based on the flow simulations, three tool areas were selected for the implementation of the optimization measures. These were evaluated with the help of the SPH simulation and compared with regard to their cooling lubricant flow behavior. Firstly, the chip mouth opening on the drill head was widened in the area of the outer cutting edge to optimize chip removal and prevent chip clogging. Furthermore, the inner contour of the drill head was adapted to a rotor shape. This ensures that the tool rotation transfers the rotational energy to the swarf and accelerates the fluid. Furthermore, the cooling lubricant outlet holes on the drill head were varied in their shape and inclination. This results in a targeted supply of coolant in the direction of the chip formation zone with increased flow velocity, which can reduce tool wear and temperatures in the process. The flow-optimized drill head shape selected on the basis of the simulation was additively manufactured from the tool steel X3NiCoMoTi18-9-5 (1.2709) using the laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) process. Post-machining was only required in the close-tolerance areas of the indexable insert seats, the guide pad seats and the connecting thread.

The performance of the flow-optimized additive manufactured drill heads was analyzed in experimental tests. It was found that the optimized geometry in the area of the coolant outlets and the modified chip mouth have a positive effect on the cooling lubricant flow and the removal of chips. The ejector effect, which is essential for ejector drilling and is responsible for the negative pressure in the inner tube, occurred at a significantly lower volume flow. The experiments demonstrate that a complete avoidance of chip clogging and the resulting drill head wear is achieved, resulting in a longer tool life of the outer cutting edge. Thanks to the simulation-based design of the drill head, an energy-efficient, resource-saving and process-reliable deep hole drilling process could be realized. For cutting speeds of $v_c = 80$ m/min and a feed rate of $f = 0.2$ mm, the required coolant volume flow rate could be reduced by up to 42.72 % ($\dot{V}_z = 29.5$ l/min) compared to the standard tool ($\dot{V}_z = 51.5$ l/min).

2.2 Development of advanced particle-damped tool holders to increase process stability in wide parameter ranges

When implementing efficient cutting processes, negative effects such as the occurrence of unwanted process vibrations, which are associated with higher cutting parameters, often prevent an increase in productivity. This occurs in particular when the stability of the machine tool is low, with long overhanging tools and when machining demanding materials that tend to form segmented chips. The process vibrations have a negative effect on tool wear and the resulting machining quality. Additive manufacturing enables the realization of complex particle-filled structures inside tool holders. The effect of these particle dampers is based on impact and friction processes between the individual particles in the cavity, which dissipate vibration energy from the system and dampen the machining process.

As part of the investigations, indexable insert holders and HSK63 tool holders were manufactured from tool steel X3NiCoMoTi18-9-5 (1.2709) using the LPBF process. The shape of the cavities and the inner structure made of modified truncated octahedron elements is based on preliminary investigations and was constructed using parameterized algorithms [7]. **Figure 2** shows the design of an additively manufactured indexable insert holder on the left with a cross-section of the cavity including the inner structure. The HSK63 tool holder shown on the

right has a hybrid structure and is created using a conventionally manufactured HSK63 blank as the basis for the additively manufactured part containing the particle damper.

Figure 2: Additively manufactured tool holders for turning (left) and milling (right) with integrated particle dampers, surface quality and acceleration measurements for turning HSX®130 (middle)

In addition to the shape and surface structure of the cavity, the detailed investigations of the integrated particle dampers also focused on the powder material and the filling level of the cavity. In turning tests, a 50% filling of the cavity with WC-ZrO₂ particles was identified as particularly suitable. The middle of Figure 2 shows the measurement results for turning experiments of the bainitic steel HSX®130. The results of the conventional holder in red show a comparatively poor surface characterized by process vibrations and chatter marks, while the surface when using the particle-damped holder (green) is characterized only by feed marks. The acceleration measurements in the cutting and feed direction also demonstrate the excellent effect of the particle damper.

In relation to investigations with the additively manufactured HSK63 tool holder during milling, a 50% WC-ZrO₂ filling also has the greatest damping effect [8]. The harmonic response functions were determined with the aid of targeted excitation of the tool system using an impulse hammer. A simulative estimation of the stability limits was used to identify interesting speed ranges for the detailed experimental analyses. In comparison between a conventional tool holder and the additive manufactured holder with particle damping, the cutting depth up to the occurrence of chatter vibrations and thus the minimum reference stability limit could be increased by at least 146%. The use of tool holders with particle damping thus leads to a significant damping of process vibrations in both turning and milling operations. This enables more efficient and productive machining processes by realizing better component qualities and increasing productivity through the use of higher cutting parameters. Reduced tool wear enables the resource-efficient use of tools and leads to energy savings, as the manufacture and reconditioning of tools must be taken into account when assessing machining processes.

3 Potential to improve the resource-efficient use of cutting tools due to the analysis and understanding of the interactions in their reprocessing

In addition to improving tools and the machining processes themselves, companies are increasingly focusing on the manufacture and reconditioning of machining tools when considering their overall energy and resource efficiency. A key part of the endeavor to reduce CO₂ emissions and uncover optimization potential is the accurate quantification of a company's carbon footprint.

The Greenhouse Gas Protocol provides an internationally recognized framework for quantifying and reporting greenhouse gas emissions. It divides emissions into three areas: Scope 1 comprises direct emissions from own or controlled sources, Scope 2 refers to indirect emissions from the consumption of purchased energy, and Scope 3 includes all other indirect emissions along the value chain. In order to be able to calculate Scope 3 for parts production as well, the footprint of the cutting tools must be known. The production route of cemented carbide tools was therefore analyzed using the example of a 6.8 mm solid cemented carbide drill. The manufacturing route of a cemented carbide twist drill initially comprises the production of blanks, whereby powder production, moulding and sintering are important in addition to the extraction of raw materials. This is followed by the process steps of grinding the sintered blank. The ground tool body is usually subjected to cutting edge

preparation and finally coated. A worn tool can be reconditioned after use by regrinding the tool and subjecting it to cutting edge preparation and coating again. To quantify this, the individual tool manufacturing processes were analyzed step by step. At the same time, a three-phase power measurement of the system and all peripheral devices, such as cooling lubricant pumps, was carried out on the machine tools. This made it possible to determine the electrical energy required to manufacture a single drill. **Figure 3** shows the relative results of these measurements.

Figure 3: Energy consumption in the production of a solid carbide twist drill with d = 6.8 mm.

The investigations into the manufacture of cemented carbide tools have yielded key findings. In particular, the high proportion of secondary processes, such as the provision of compressed air and cooling lubricant, was identified as a significant energy consumer. This indicates a large optimization potential that can be realized through a targeted and adapted supply of these media. In addition, the investigations show that reconditioning worn tools can lead to considerable savings in electrical energy and the associated emissions. This enables companies to significantly reduce their CO₂ footprint in production without significantly affecting tool life. A circular economy should be the overall aim, whereby tools that can no longer be reground should be fed into the recycling process separately according to their carbide composition.

The high proportion of cylindrical grinding processes should be noted, which is explained by the time-intensive nature of these processes on tool grinding machines. More resource-efficient production could be achieved through the use of cylindrical grinding machines. In future, the centerless grinding of the sintered blank and secondary processes such as washing and cutting should also be included in the analyses in order to identify further potential for optimization.

As Figure 3 shows, a high amount of energy is necessary for the production of the blanks of cemented carbide cutting tools. The reprocessing of worn tools offers the opportunity to extend their life cycle. Therefore, it contributes to the enhancement of the sustainability of the use of the tools as well as to the saving and efficient use of resources. In this context, the process route for the reprocessing of cemented carbide cutting tools has to ensure highly-productive cutting tools. Moreover, the process chain of the reprocessing has to fulfill economic achievements as well. In order to contribute to both, research concerning the reprocessing of cemented carbide drilling tools is focused in a collaborative project together with the GFE - Gesellschaft für Fertigungstechnik und Entwicklung Schmalkalden e.V. and partners from industry. The reprocessing of drilling tools comprises several process steps, which are shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4: Process steps in the reprocessing of cemented carbide cutting tools

Initially, the process configurations and the influences of the individual process steps of de-coating, re-grinding or the post-treatment on the substrate and the tool performance are examined. Based on that, different process routes along the process chain in reprocessing shall be conducted and their influence on the performance and on economic aspects should be considered. The main focus will be on the interactions between the process steps as they are a key factor to build a fundamental understanding for the reliable reprocessing of cemented carbide cutting tools.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

High demands on productivity with a simultaneous focus on resource-efficient production with the lowest possible waste, low energy consumption and a small carbon footprint require continuous developments of tools and processes and the detailed analysis of process chains. This is the only way to identify and exploit available savings potential. As part of the investigations described, great progress was made through the use of innovative and complex simulation systems, targeted tool optimization with the help of additive manufacturing and detailed analysis of the energy consumption of numerous process steps in the life cycle of a cutting tool. In addition to reducing the energy required for the cooling lubricant supply and increasing productivity in turning and milling by means of particle-damped tool holders, a better understanding of the energy consumption in the production of cutting tools in particular provides approaches for making machining processes more efficient in the future.

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